

BEYOND INFORMATION: HOW RELIGIOUS BELIEFS SHAPE MIGRATION DECISION-MAKING

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Key Issues

- The European Union (EU) and/or individual Member States continue to invest heavily in migration information campaigns, despite limited evidence of their effectiveness.
- Potential migrants place greater trust in social networks and personal contacts than in EU-funded campaigns.
- Migration decisions are shaped by different factors of influence, of which information is only one element.
- Beyond tangible considerations, intangible factors, including religious and spiritual beliefs, play a decisive role in shaping migration decision-making.
- The EU should prioritise investment in legal and sustainable migration pathways over further expansion of migration information campaigns, whose impact on migration decisions remains limited.

The EU and/or individual Member States have invested significant resources in efforts to control irregularised migration before migrants reach EU borders. Migration information campaigns have become a prominent tool in this strategy. Unlike 'hard' border control tools such as detention and deportation, migration information campaigns are often described as 'soft' forms of border control. These campaigns target potential migrants in countries of origin

and transit. They use carefully designed messages to influence migration-related perceptions and decisions.

Information campaigns are premised on three key assumptions: First, potential migrants lack adequate information about the risks of the migration trajectory they intend to embark on. In addition, they may be insufficiently informed about the rules governing the entry of non-citizens in destination countries. Second, their knowledge prior to being exposed to migration information campaigns is incomplete and inaccurate. Third, migration information campaigns can influence the migration decision-making of potential migrants. Based on these assumptions, the EU and/or Member States promote three main messages: “there are opportunities at home, stay”; “the route is dangerous, do not go”; “life in Europe is difficult, do not come”. This policy brief draws on empirical research undertaken within the [H2020 BRIDGES project](#), with a particular focus on the influence of [EU-funded information campaigns on migration decisions in The Gambia](#). It particularly incorporates insights from my [article](#) on the role of predestination thinking in migration decision-making, based on data generated by the project. It shows that potential migrants often possess adequate information and accurate information about the journey that they intend to undertake. It also finds that migration information campaigns play only a limited role in their migration decision-making. These findings challenge the assumptions on which such campaigns are based.

The brief demonstrates how potential migrants deploy counter-narratives to the three main EU campaign narratives. First, they challenge claims about opportunities at home, pointing to unequal access to support, their concentration in urban areas, and the lack of post-training assistance. Second, many argue that, despite the challenges of life in Europe for an irregularised migrant, it remains preferable to conditions in The Gambia. Third, they contest the warnings about the dangers of the migration route by drawing on practical coping strategies and religious beliefs.

More importantly, the findings suggest that religious and spiritual beliefs can shape migration decisions as much as, and sometimes more than, information or socio-economic factors. Current EU deterrence narratives pay insufficient attention to these embedded belief systems and their influence on migration decision-making.

HOW EFFECTIVE ARE THESE EU AND/OR MEMBER STATE-FUNDED CAMPAIGNS?

There is little evidence that migration information campaigns significantly influence the migration decisions of potential migrants. [Several studies](#) have shown that the negative narratives about migration and Europe as a destination deployed in information campaigns do not align with the more positive local narratives about migration and Europe. The message that there are opportunities at home is generally acknowledged, but often quickly challenged by arguing the disparity in terms of access, especially between urban and rural dwellers. Others argue that support provided through EU-funded projects is often short-lived and insufficient. Once projects end, opportunities to continue are limited. For some, this reinforces their desire to embark on illegalised migration. The message that life in Europe is difficult is widely contested. Potential migrants often cite success stories shared by friends and relatives living in Europe. These accounts carry considerable weight. They are further reinforced by positive images and stories about Europe that many people encountered while growing up. In contrast, messages about the dangers of the migration route tend to align with local understandings and experiences. Potential migrants generally acknowledge these risks. Yet recognition of danger does not necessarily deter irregularised migration. Instead, many describe practical coping strategies or, more importantly, draw on religious and spiritual beliefs to manage uncertainty and risk.

THE PRIMACY OF BELIEF SYSTEMS IN MIGRATION DECISION-MAKING

Migration information campaigns are built on the assumption that providing more information can influence migration decisions. They also assume that addressing structural drivers, such as poverty and unemployment, will reduce irregularised migration. While this is true to some extent, they do not fully take into consideration how migration decisions are made. Many potential migrants remain aware of the risks associated with irregularised migration, yet still choose to undertake these journeys. This is precisely where the role of beliefs comes in. In The Gambia, such beliefs are deeply embedded in everyday life and decision-making. Many people understood major life events, whether positive or negative, as part of God's will. Migration was often interpreted through this same lens. Rather than being viewed solely as an economic strategy, it was frequently described as part of a broader life trajectory ordained by God.

This finding has important implications for migration governance. EU information campaigns are largely designed around a rational-choice model of decision-making. They assume that individuals weigh risks and opportunities and then adjust their behaviour when presented with new information. However, my findings suggest that migration decisions are also shaped by spiritual and religious frameworks that influence how migration decisions are interpreted. Information is not simply received; it is filtered through existing systems of meaning and belief.

For many participants, migration was understood as a rite of passage and an experience that they were destined to undergo at some point in their lives. As a result, migration was often framed not as a question of whether one would migrate, but when and through which route. Within this worldview, deterrence messages have limited influence because they do not challenge the underlying belief that migration forms part of a divinely ordained life course.

Religious and spiritual beliefs also shape how risks are understood and managed. Many participants acknowledged the dangers highlighted in EU campaigns. Yet they often expressed a strong conviction that divine protection would accompany them on the journey. This belief was not necessarily seen as contradicting awareness of risk. Instead, it provided a framework for coping with uncertainty and risk. Divine protection was expected to manifest through encounters with trustworthy people, safe passage across dangerous routes, access to reliable smugglers, or protection from accidents, violence, and exploitation. In some cases, beliefs about divine destiny extended even to the possibility of death. Participants argued that if death occurred during the journey, it would reflect God's predetermined plan rather than a failure of individual judgment. This belief does not eliminate perceptions of danger. Rather, it changes the meaning attached to risk and the extent to which risk can be mitigated through information alone. Consequently, campaigns that emphasise the possibility of death or suffering may have limited persuasive power among audiences who view such outcomes as ultimately determined by divine will.

These findings do not suggest that information is irrelevant. Instead, they indicate that information constitutes only one element of migration decision-making. Religious and spiritual belief systems shape how information is interpreted, how risks are evaluated, and how future outcomes are imagined. Policies that overlook these dimensions risk overestimating the influence of information campaigns and underestimating the social and cultural contexts in which migration decisions are made.

CONCLUDING REFLECTIONS

The insights presented in this brief highlight a significant gap between the assumptions underpinning EU migration campaigns and the realities of migration decision-making among their intended audiences. Despite substantial investments in such campaigns, there is limited evidence that information alone can meaningfully influence migration decisions. The findings, therefore, challenge approaches that treat irregularised migration primarily as a consequence of information deficits or inaccurate perceptions. Instead, they point to the importance of understanding migration decision-making within the broader social, cultural, and religious contexts in which it is embedded. Recognising these dynamics is essential for a more complete understanding of why many potential migrants continue to pursue irregularised migration despite being aware of the risk. More importantly, resources currently allocated to these campaigns could be more effectively directed toward expanding legal, safe, and sustainable pathways for regular migration.

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